

Critical Thinking And Outcome-Focused Teaching Among Araling Panlipunan Teachers

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Abstract. The study assessed the extent of critical thinking ability and outcome-focused teaching among Teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores, Pearson r correlation, and Linear Regression, where results were treated with confidentiality following research ethics. Findings revealed that the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in Cateel 2 District in terms of learning characteristics, experiential knowledge, interpersonal skills, and technical skills was extensive, as well as outcome-focused teaching among teachers regarding assessment-infused activities and intended learning outcomes. There is a significant relationship between critical thinking abilities and outcome-focused teaching. Indicators of critical thinking abilities provided, namely experiential knowledge, technical skills, and interpersonal skills, indicate statistically significant influence outcome-focused. Further studies may look to other factors that contribute to the improvement of outcome-focused teaching and may sustain the practices in intensifying critical thinking abilities in pedagogy and assessment through collaboration among teachers and their respective schools to do the same and continuously improve themselves.

KEY WORDS

1. Critical Thinking 2. Outcome-focused teaching 3. Araling Panlipunan

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1. Introduction

Across the globe, Teachers reported in schools where it had been observed and explored whether teachers stayed in the profession or exited during this time of uncertainty (Aundrain et al., 2021). The professional lives of teachers are in an incredible upheaval due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which has potential implications for the teaching profession and the workforce. The ambiguity of what schools will look like in the future and growing disparities of children have teachers concerned that their jobs are more untenable than ever. The vital importance of quality teachers is indisputable. Much has been written about the teacher shortage and the growing need for teachers not only in the United States but across the globe (Evans et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2016), as discussed by Audrain (2021). For many years, all eyes have been on recruitment and retention, alternative pathways to teacher preparation, and a decrease in the rigors of teacher preparation. However, with the crisis comes an opportunity to examine

the working conditions of teachers, the teaching profession, and the learning environment in new ways (Vegas Winthrop, 2020). Many countries have been looking for a workforce that can deepen and personalize learning for students by building teams, distributing expertise, increasing specializations, and creating more opportunities for advancement. It is a time to leapfrog, to take advantage of the upheaval to put the puzzle pieces back together in new ways, new shapes, and new formations. It is critical that we examine what is happening with the education workforce and understand the existing complexities of the teaching profession, acknowledge the chaos of the pandemic, examine what has happened to teachers over the past year, and think anew with urgency and creativity. Teachers play an influential role in society as well as in the lives of youth and caregivers. Unfortunately, the profession of teaching in the U.S. has faced some longstanding and menacing challenges that frequently serve to undermine its reputation. Considerations such as rigorous training and licensing, favorable working conditions related to demands and environments, substantial workplace agency, and relatively high compensation are defining characteristics of the status of a profession. Plummer et al. (2022) note that while some individuals argue that instilling an ethos of public service and high standards among teachers is sufficient to elevate the profession in the eyes of educators themselves as well as society, others maintain that a mere shift in sentiment is simply not enough. Rather, transformations of the characteristics that define the profession itself, including teachers' organizational and working conditions, are essential (Situmorang et al., 2022). Further, Fang (2022) illustrates some of the current unfavorable working conditions teachers face when they write, teachers often are isolated in their classrooms, face overwhelming noninstructional duties, have extremely limited opportunities for meaningful decision-making, lack basic instructional ma-

terials, and perceive few opportunities for advancement and growth. These impact the reputation of the teaching profession in the eyes of society as well as from the perspectives of teachers, which has far-reaching implications for teachers and students alike. One salient consequence is the nationwide crisis in the U.S. with recruiting, training, and retaining individuals in the teaching workforce (Bozkurt, 2020). In the Philippines, teaching is described as a complex practice (Ball Forzani, 2009), with roles being multi-dimensional and unpredictable (Doyle, 1977) as discussed by Renton (2020). Some have described the work as "highly improvisational and wholly context-dependent" (Ball and Forzani, 2009, p. 503). Thus, teaching can be extremely daunting for novice teachers, who are expected to support students to achieve the same outcomes as their expert counterparts. The pressure on teacher education is immense; it can either help to make the case for or inhibit teaching's status as a profession. The current full face-to-face implementation of classes, as mandated in DepED Order 36, S 2022, discussed the calendar of activities across public and private schools in the country. Efforts to encourage teacher collaboration have rarely attended to each of these aspects. Beyond removing structural and administrative barriers, teachers must learn to collaborate closely with other educators whose backgrounds and experiences may be unlike their own, leveraging the varied personal and professional experiences as assets to best meet the needs of students (Boveda and Weinberg, 2020; Weinberg and Boveda, 2021) cited by Fang (2022). The need to develop and enhance teaching facilitation and instruction is an urgent call to effectively prepare learners for life skills performance. Teaching strategies be enhanced in this current state to make the full learning and teaching process be manifested in the entire stakeholders of Davao Oriental. Thus, this paper is presented.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—This section presents a synthesis of literature on critical thinking ability and outcome-focused teaching. It includes discussions on critical thinking characteristics, experiential and technological skills, interpersonal skills, and their impact on teaching effectiveness.

1.1.1. Critical Thinking Ability—Critical thinking involves conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information (Renton, 2020). It helps individuals understand motivations, solve problems, and make informed decisions (Situmorang, 2022). Teachers with strong critical thinking skills assess teaching goals and student progress, integrating analytical and evaluative processes in education (Alharbi, 2022). Developing these skills fosters academic and job success (Xhomara, 2022). Teachers perceive critical thinking as teachable but face challenges such as inadequate curricula and overcrowded classrooms (Kanmaz, 2022).

1.1.2. Learning Characteristics—Critical thinking is integral to learning quality and must be embedded across curricula (Alsaleh, 2020). It enables students to evaluate information critically, eliminate biases, and make rational decisions (Alharbi, 2022). Saudi teachers generally support critical thinking instruction but require further training (Alharbi, 2021). Student-centered teaching strongly correlates with critical thinking skills (Xhomara, 2022). Effective questioning fosters engagement and higher-order thinking (Maison et al., 2022). However, students may not fully acquire critical thinking skills despite educators' efforts (Evangelisto, 2021). Writing instruction does not automatically enhance critical thinking, requiring explicit teaching strategies (Karanja, 2021).

1.1.3. Experiential Knowledge—Experiential learning enhances critical thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving (Coleman et al., 2022). It fosters reflection, preparing students for real-world applications (Amolloh, 2018). Simulation-based experiential learning signifi-

cantly improves problem-solving skills (Uzun Uygun, 2022). Integrated teaching in social studies promotes engagement and meaningful learning (Olovsson, 2021). Social studies textbooks should incorporate critical perspectives (Hansen Puustinen, 2021). Effective vocabulary and comprehension instruction enhance content learning (Capin et al., 2021). Literary materials improve student engagement in social studies (Sömen, 2021).

1.1.4. Technical Skills—Technical skills are essential in education, particularly in technology, math, and science (Coleman et al., 2020). Educators need domain expertise and instructional competence (Kyeremeh et al., 2022). Inquiry-based learning enhances teaching practices (Wong et al., 2019). Employers value both technical and soft skills, such as communication and teamwork (Warner, 2020). Intelligence and mind games improve academic performance (Cagir Oruc, 2020). Digital tools like dynamic maps enhance global awareness (Ineç, 2021). Argumentation-based learning and educational games foster critical engagement (Bulut et al., 2019; Karaman et al., 2022). Writing-to-learn strategies develop critical thinking in prospective teachers (Kayaalp et al., 2020). Digital learning improves students' social skills (Sariyatun et al., 2021).

1.1.5. Interpersonal Skills—Interpersonal skills, including empathy, active listening, and social awareness, are crucial in teaching (Coleman et al., 2020). Teachers must effectively communicate, collaborate, and manage conflicts (Speicher, 2021). Experiential learning supports professional competence and teaching preparedness (Amolloh et al., 2018). Social studies promote self-control, motivation, and collaboration (Aksüt, 2020; Aktan, 2019; Suh Hinton, 2021). Cooperative learning enhances preschoolers' social skills (Polat et al., 2022). Teachers perceive gaps in self-efficacy for specific skills in the curriculum (Seker, 2021).

1.1.6. Outcome-Focused Teaching—Outcome-based education (OBE) prioritizes measurable learning goals (Polat et al., 2022). Professional development enhances teaching quality, focusing on collaborative learning strategies (Ahmad Zaky El Islami et al., 2022). Contextual and social learning approaches foster meaningful education (Koskinen Pitkäniemi, 2022). Teacher resilience influences student outcomes (Brewer et al., 2022). Institutional support is crucial for sustaining innovative teaching practices (Wise et al., 2022). Teaching-focused faculty often lack professional development opportunities (Simmons et al., 2021).

1.1.7. Intended Learning Outcomes—Guided teaching models improve student achievement (Anugrah Chandra, 2021). Self-regulation, social skills, and problem-solving abilities contribute to better learning outcomes (Maksum et al., 2021). Curriculum mapping aligns student experiences with intended learning outcomes (Labouta et al., 2019). Guided-discovery techniques enhance social studies performance (Ayodele Nasiry, 2021).

1.1.8. Activities Infused—Social studies integrate cultural, historical, and experiential learning methods. Music-supported activities improve student engagement (Goksu, 2020). Museum-based learning deepens historical understanding (Uztemur et al., 2019). Literary materials foster classroom participation (Sömen, 2021). QR codes and interactive learning tools enhance student motivation (Karakus Seyihoglu, 2022).

1.1.9. Assessment—Constructive alignment in education improves learning outcomes (Hailikari et al., 2020). Digital learning platforms foster critical thinking (Evedi et al., 2022). Social work educators emphasize analytical skills and intellectual curiosity in assessments (Hall et al., 2021).

1.2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—The study is anchored on the Outcome-based education (OBE) theory as espoused by

education, in which an emphasis is placed on a clearly articulated idea of what students are expected to know and be able to do, that is, what skills and knowledge they need to have when they leave the school system. A renowned academician and psychologist, William G. Spady, best known as the "Father of Outcome-Based Education," coined the term "OBE" in the year 1988. This blog aims at helping educators, faculty, and educationalists to understand the concept of OBE and how it can help in maximizing their students' success. Outcome-based education or outcomes-based education (OBE) is an educational theory that bases each part of an educational system around goals (outcomes). By the end of the educational experience, each student should have achieved the goal. Characteristics of outcome-based education similar to mastery-based learning: There are clear criteria for what constitutes mastery. Instruction is thoughtful and adapts to learner needs. Learners are assisted when and where they have challenges. However, the biggest obstacle to designing an OBE curriculum is a lack of expertise in this area. The OBE approach is based on outcomes rather than on inputs. Outcomes are expected to be concrete and measurable and should not be subjective. Thus, this comprises four major components, namely, the curriculum design, teaching and learning methods, assessment, and continuous quality improvement and monitoring. Principles in the implementation of the OBE is focused on the idea that people should be at the center of their own care and support planning and learning, and that these learners should be actively listened to without judgement for their personal strengths should be acknowledge and reiterated through supporting what they have identified and what they want to achieve. In this study, the conceptual framework is shown in Figure 1, where the association of the critical thinking ability in terms of critical thinking characteristics, experiential knowledge, technical skills, and interpersonal skills

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

among teachers teaching Araling Panlipunan tended learning outcomes, the activities infused are assumed to have influenced their outcome- and the forms and types of assessment they perform to learners. focused teaching in terms of designing the in-

1.3. Statement of the Problem—The study teaching among Teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental Division. This specifically sought to answer the following statement of the problem:

- (1) What is the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in Cateel 2 District in terms of;
 - (1) learning characteristics;
 - (2) experiential knowledge;
 - (3) technical skills; and
 - (4) interpersonal skills?
- (2) What is the extent of outcome-focused teaching in terms of;
 - (1) intended learning outcome;
 - (2) activities infused; and,
 - (3) assessment?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between critical thinking ability and outcome-focused teaching among teachers?
- (4) Which among the indicators of critical thinking ability significantly influence the level of outcome-focused teaching among teachers in Cateel 2 District?

1.4. Hypotheses —To provide empirical evidence given the posed theoretical and conceptual frameworks as claimed by the study, null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance, stating: Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between critical thinking ability and outcome-focused teaching among teachers. and, Ho 2: None of the indicators of critical thinking ability significantly influence outcome-focused teaching among teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental Division. This proposed study emphasized the importance of the results given gathered data, analysis, interpretations, and implications to the real world. The reflections coming from the possible results will be a sound output for the stakeholders of the school and the whole learning community for cyclical planning. Results will be of

significance to the following: School Principals. The manager and leader of the curriculum and instruction mechanism. The leadership and management in the delivery of the curriculum are expected to be through technical assistance and instructional supervision to augment curriculum and instruction delivery among teachers in Araling Panlipunan. Given face-to-face learning, the results of the study will provide information to school heads on the importance of having sound instructional leadership that facilitates sound teaching interests and motivation to increase academic performance and life skills among learners. This will be a good input to the next cycle of planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation in the management and delivery of curriculum and instruction and for further continuous improvement and high job satisfaction. Teachers. Facilitators of learning across learning areas and providers of learning materials to make learning more meaningful. Given the new normal and full swing of face-to-face classes, Teachers are expected to determine the essentials of learning given learners are having the transition from the non-face-to-face and face-to-face interactions of learning. The results of the study will provide inputs to teachers on the creativity and soundness of critical thinking abilities to ensure that expected deliverables given the academic performances of learners are expected. Parents. These are the people who are the direct partners of the teachers in the delivery and management of the curriculum. The new school year 2022-2023 calls for the cooperation of parents to support their elementary school learners to increase learning performance. Given the full implementation of face-to-face classes, parents are likewise expected to give support. The results of the study will encourage and escalate participation in the augmentation and availabil-

ity of school facilities to be able to connect with learners on the process of learning in the new normal. Future Researchers. Policy implications on the expected output of this study shall facilitate the next step forward among future researchers to come up with a sound idea as to where to take off to continuously measure evidence of good practices in the implementation of curriculum delivery, instruction, and assessment governance and operations amongst Public Elementary Schools teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This study defined the terms conceptually and operationally to better understand and reference them when discussing results in the preceding chapters. Critical Thinking Ability. The term refers to the ability to analyze facts and form a judgment. It is a form of emotional intelligence. Someone with critical thinking skills can think clearly and rationally when the situation demands it. It allows them to perform problem-solving and decision-making more effectively. In this study, the term is used as the independent variable where indicators are the critical thinking characteristics, experiential knowledge, technical skills, and inferential skills among teachers in Araling Panlipunan Junior High School Level. Outcome-focused Teaching. The term refers to a learner-centered approach to facilitation of learning that focuses on what a student should be able to do in the real world upon completion of their course or program. It is flexible, empowerment-oriented approach to learning. It aims at equipping learners with the knowledge, competence, and orientation needed for success after they leave school. Hence its guiding vision is that of a competent future citizen. In this study, the term is used as the dependent variable and the predictor of critical thinking ability. Indicators are intended learning outcomes, activities infused, and assessment.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains a discussion of the technical method used in the study. This includes the selection of the study's design, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical consideration, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are essential to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. This refers to studies that describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. Further, the study variables are classified as independent predictors and dependent outcomes. Moreover, any scientific process begins with a description, based on observation, of an event or events, from which theories may later be developed to explain the observations (Pallant, 2020). On the other hand, this type of research tries to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities in order to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). In this study, indicators under the independent variable, critical thinking ability, shall be measured it's the extent of critical thinking characteristics, experiential knowledge, technical skills, and interpersonal skills and its significant correlation with the dependent variable, outcome-focused teaching level among junior high school teachers on the intended learning outcome, activities infused and assessment in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Using the design mentioned, it is assumed that variables, along with the indicators mentioned, the researcher empirically provides evidence that the presented hypothesis shall be null and void in nature.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary Teachers of Cateel 2 District Schools, Davao Oriental. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective school within the district.

Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face considering the availability of Wi-Fi Connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. As much as possible, these teacher-respondents were seasoned teachers in the respective schools to measure competence and how they performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and to the learning effectiveness in Araling Panlipunan given the new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings, including SLAC sessions on the pedagogies in teaching Araling Panlipunan. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This proposed research study used an adapted survey instrument. The researcher took time to gather and read reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content of the instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literature as argued by the authors. Two parts of the survey questionnaire measured the extent of teachers' critical thinking abilities through critical thinking characteristics, experiential knowledge, technical skills, and interpersonal skills. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the level of outcome-

focused teaching along with the indicators, intended learning outcome, activities infused, and assessment. Based on the definition of the variables, the statements of the survey were placed in contexts. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence. They generated an alpha Cron-

bach of 0.887, which means that 88.7 percent level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of teachers' critical thinking abilities. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' critical thinking abilities are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' critical thinking abilities are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' critical thinking abilities are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' critical thinking abilities are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' critical thinking abilities are not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the level of outcome-focused teaching, a 5-point Likert

scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Effective	The outcome-focused teaching is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Effective	The outcome-focused teaching is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Effective	The outcome-focused teaching is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Effective	The outcome-focused teaching is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective	The outcome-focused teaching is not manifested

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The preceding statements explain the data-gathering procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guide-

lines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data, most especially in the current full face-to-face interaction. Permission to conduct the

study. In the second week of January 2023, the researcher started to prepare documents such as letter requests for the conduct of the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004) and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the schools of Cateel 2 District Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of January 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of February 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime in the fourth week of February 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of March 2023.

2.5. Ethical Considerations —The researcher sought guidance and advice from the thesis adviser. This resulted in proper authorization, and consent was obtained from the re-

spondents of the study to ensure that all their rights would be fully protected, specifically in handling the data, however, not limited to:

Social Value – Research plays a vital role in society, and this study specifically focuses on the collaborative support system among teachers and their motivation to teach, particularly in the context of elementary education. I am particularly interested in exploring how digital text reading and comprehension among students are influenced by teachers' teaching efficacy. This research could inform policymakers and educators in developing programs and solutions that will ultimately benefit learners. The researcher views social value as a crucial criterion for ensuring ethical research practices. This refers to the anticipated benefits that a research intervention can provide to the well-being of society or its members. Ethical considerations in research are essential for safeguarding the rights and welfare of participants. Some key ethical concerns include maintaining participant anonymity, avoiding the collection of personally identifiable information, and ensuring that participants' identities remain confidential.

Voluntary Participation – The researcher considered several ethical considerations to ensure that the study was conducted appropriately. To comply with ethical considerations in conducting research, all participants were provided with informed consent to participate in the survey. This indicated that the participation of respondents was voluntary in nature. Also, the purpose and benefits of the research are to explain to the respondents, and the respondents were informed that should they wish to withdraw at any point during the data-gathering procedure, they could do so (Lotich, 2011).

Privacy and Confidentiality – The profile of the study respondents was considered and treated with utmost confidentiality to protect their rights, especially since the respondents are public school teachers. Privacy and confidentiality were specifically observed through the pre-

sentation and discussions of results (Koenig MacMillan, 2004).

Informed Consent – It further explained to the respondents that their information would remain private and confidential and that the specific content of individual surveys would only be discussed with the research adviser. The research adviser and the respondents were unknown to each other; thus, in the final report, the identity of the participants was removed, and pseudonyms were used. While sharing the purpose of the study with the respondents, the researcher also shared their background and some of the researcher's personal stories as a professional woman in the teaching industry. This helps build trust and, in turn, encourages the respondents to answer the survey honestly. Such interactions were done through messenger and face-to-face in a conversation where the respondent's comfortability is considered.

Risks – Moreover, the researcher informed the respondents that their participation in the survey would not bring any foreseeable risks to their health or well-being. Thus, the respondents were informed that if they became upset or distressed as a result of answering the questions that are part of the researcher's standard battery, then the researcher would have helped them obtain a referral for the respondent to see a trained professional who can help process these feelings (Lotich, 2011). The researcher shall then make some alternatives to complete the data collection.

Benefits – Further, the observable benefits of the study were immediately disseminated to the stakeholders. The findings of the study generated facts that are important for enhancing the students' well-being (Koenig MacMillan, 2004). This served as the basis for educational institutions to pay attention to creating a learning environment for teachers to become more productive and active in facilitating learning competencies in Araling Panlipunan.

Plagiarism – Furthermore, the researcher

strictly adhered to other ethical issues, which include plagiarism, fabrication, and falsification (Lakey and Cohen, 2020). The researcher ensured that the resources being used in this study are properly cited. The authors' ideas are paraphrased and properly synthesized to abstain from plagiarism. The researcher made conclusions that were only found from the study results. In the event of any unintentional plagiarized, fabricated, or falsified ideas, the researcher immediately revised the manuscript (Lotich, 2011).

Fabrication – The researcher guaranteed that provisions on deceit and conflict of interest were strictly observed. The researcher assured the respondents that the study was done honestly and transparently. Evidence shows that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweighs any potential harm to them (Creswell, 2014). The researcher assisted the respondents satisfactorily and talked through the study's process and outcome. They were given a general idea of what the researcher was investigating and why such a study was conducted. Their role and contribution to the study were promptly explained. **Falsification.** This study complied with the citation rules set based on APA 7th edition citation format to avoid misrepresenting work or altering any data gathered in the study (Cohen, 2020). The data and information that were written were presented in the most accurate way possible.

Conflict of Interest – The researcher ensured that conflict of interest (COI) in this study was highly observed (Lotich, 2011). There is no set of conditions for professional judgment concerning primary interest, as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tend to be influenced by secondary interests such as financial or academic gains or any forms of recognition. **Deceit.** The writings of this paper did not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm anyone, especially the respondents, since all information written was checked and validated by

the panel of experts (Lakey Cohen, 2020). Permission from the Organization/Location. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher procured a letter duly signed by the Dean of Graduate School and provided it to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental. Then, the reply from the said office allowing the researcher to conduct the study was delivered to the school principals where the study was conducted. Authorship. Finally, upon the approval of the final version to be published, the researcher considered for the authorship of the adviser and a few other individuals, such as colleagues who gave substantial contributions to the conception and design of the study, acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data and drafting the manuscript or revising it critically for important intellectual content as co-authors (Lotich, 2011). Respondents can contact the researcher at the mobile number and email address given on the informed consent form if they have questions, concerns, or complaints about the research. The researcher also ensured that the study's benefits

would be shared during meetings and conferences, with stakeholders as part of the audience.

2.6. Data Analysis —Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of critical thinking ability of teachers, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of outcome-focused teaching in Cateel 2 District. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between critical thinking ability and the outcome-focused teaching in Cateel 2 District. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4 on the indicators of the extent of critical thinking ability that significantly influence the level of outcome-focused teaching among teachers in Cateel 2 District (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations are then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data gathered in tabular and textual form to provide clear ideas and information on the queries based on the statement of the problem posed. Various reviews present implications of the results to corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as claimed and posed in the study.

3.1. The Extent Of Critical Thinking Ability Among Elementary Teachers —Critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action. Critical thinking helps people better understand themselves, their motivations, and their goals. When you can deduce information to find the most important parts and apply those to your life, you can change your situation and promote

personal growth and overall happiness. Abilities like asking questions, gathering relevant information, thinking through solutions and conclusions, and considering alternative systems of thought are a few basics of critical thinking (Renton, 2020).

3.1.1. Learning Characteristics —Indicated in Table 1 is the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in terms of learning characteristics among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: expressing appreciation of human

differences related to values, culture, personality, or learning style preferences; adapting to preferences when feasible (4.28); changing approaches as needed to get the best results (4.25), showing authentic self; demonstrates behaviors that indicate stated values (4.21), showing that teachers' critical thinking abilities are always manifested thus, very extensive. meanwhile, clarifying biases, inclinations, strengths, and limitations; acknowledging when thinking may be influenced by emotions or self-interest (4.16) and carefully considering the meaning of data and interpersonal interactions; asks asking for feedback; corrects own thinking, alert to potential errors by self and others, finds ways to avoid future mistakes (4.13) are oftentimes manifested, thus extensive. The overall mean rating of the extent of critical thinking ability in terms

of learning characteristics is 4.20, suggesting teachers' critical thinking abilities are always manifested, thus, very extensive. This indicates that the schools in Cateel 2 District are always exploring the strategies of critical thinking abilities to improve teaching in Araling Panlipuan. Strong teachers think critically. They practice the thinking art of analyzing and evaluating as they consider both day-to-day activities and long-term teaching and learning goals. They evaluate what they have, determine what they will need, and decide how and when to assess student progress. In its most basic expression, critical thinking occurs when students are analyzing, evaluating, interpreting, or synthesizing information and applying creative thought to form an argument, solve a problem, or reach a conclusion (Alharbi, 2022).

Table 1. The Extent of Critical Thinking Ability in Terms of Learning Characteristics

No	Learning Characteristics	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Clarifies biases, inclinations, strengths, and limitations; acknowledges when thinking may be influenced by emotions or self-interest.	4.16	Extensive
2	Shows authentic self; demonstrates behaviors that indicate stated values.	4.21	Very Extensive
3	Expresses appreciation of human differences related to values, culture, personality, or learning style preferences; adapts to preferences when feasible.	4.28	Very Extensive
4	Carefully considers the meaning of data and interpersonal interactions, asks for feedback, corrects own thinking, is alert to potential errors by self and others, and finds ways to avoid future mistakes.	4.13	Extensive
5	Changes approaches as needed to get the best results.	4.25	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.20	Very Extensive

Learning characteristics related to Critical Thinking (CT) have been recognized as one of the most important thinking skills and one of the

most important indicators of student learning quality. In order to develop successful critical thinkers, CT must be incorporated into the cur-

riculum content and teaching approaches and sequenced at all grade levels. Alsaleh (2020) provides a systematic review of the extant literature on teaching CT skills. The comprehensive review led to the building of a conceptual framework that discusses the four main debates among the researchers engaged in the field of teaching CT. The study of actual practices indicates that teaching approaches tend to focus on subject content rather than CT development. The results indicate a gap in teaching CT skills in terms of innovative methods and particularly in the use of new technologies. On the other hand, Saudi teachers are unsure how to include critical thinking into their classrooms, vis a vis learning characteristic. Alharbi (2021) aimed at identifying the knowledge of Saudi teachers regarding critical thinking skills and exploring their attitudes towards improving Saudi students' critical thinking skills. The results revealed that the level of Saudi Teachers' knowledge of critical thinking skills was high and that their attitudes towards improving students' critical thinking skills were positive. Meanwhile, Xhomara (2022) aimed to investigate the impact of a student-centered teaching approaches, personalized learning, and previous education achievements on critical thinking skills. It is found that there is a strong positive correlation between student-centered teaching and critical thinking skills. Meanwhile, personalized learning, as well as previous education achievements, correlates positively and significantly with critical thinking skills. Student-centered teaching and previous education achievements are strong predictors of critical thinking skills. Results implied that when teachers develop such skills, this helps students to filter the wheat from the chaff, intellectually speaking. Developing strong critical thinking skills helps students to eliminate dubious data to leave only the strongest, most reliable information. At its core, critical thinking is about having good reasons for our beliefs. It helps to navigate through bias our own and that

of others to avoid manipulation or becoming enslaved by our feelings. These are essential skills in an age of overwhelming information.

3.1.2. Experiential Knowledge —Shown in Table 2 is the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in terms of experiential knowledge among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: looks for changes in circumstances that warrant a need to modify thinking or approaches (4.20) is always manifested; offers alternative solutions and approaches; comes up with useful ideas (4.19) and shows tolerance for different viewpoints; questions how own viewpoints are influencing thinking (4.15) are oftentimes manifested, while, carefully considers meaning of data and interpersonal interactions, asks for feedback; corrects own thinking, alert to potential errors by self and others, finds ways to avoid future mistakes (3.26) and expresses faith in ability to reason and learn; overcomes disappointments (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of the extent of critical thinking ability in terms of experiential knowledge is 3.80, suggesting teachers' critical thinking abilities is extensive. This indicates that the schools in Cateel 2 District are oftentimes manifesting experiential knowledge in their critical thinking abilities to improve teaching in Araling Panlipuan. Experiential knowledge is knowledge gained through experience, as opposed to a priori before experience knowledge: it can also be contrasted both with propositional textbook knowledge and with practical knowledge. Experiential [learning] is a philosophy and methodology in which educators purposefully engage with students in direct experience and focused reflection in order to increase knowledge, develop skills, and clarify values (Coleman et. al; 2022). Experiential knowledge was succinctly defined in 1994 as "information and wisdom gained from lived experience" by Marsha A. Schubert and Thomasina J. Borkman. It signi-

fies a way of knowing about and understanding things and events through direct engagement (Amolloh, 2018). Therefore, experiential education teaches students to examine their actions and their thought processes, and even their emotional responses. This internal reflection prepares students for the workplace and helps them make major life choices, improve their personal relationships, and address their emotional needs.

Table 2. Extent of Critical Thinking Ability in Terms of Experiential Knowledge

No	Experiential Knowledge	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Offers alternative solutions and approaches; comes up with useful ideas.	4.19	Extensive
2	Shows tolerance for different viewpoints; questions how own viewpoints are influencing thinking.	4.15	Extensive
3	Carefully considers the meaning of data and interpersonal interactions, asks for feedback, corrects own thinking, is alert to potential errors by self and others, and finds ways to avoid future mistakes.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
4	Expresses faith in the ability to reason and learn; overcomes disappointments.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	Looks for changes in circumstances that warrant a need to modify thinking or approaches.	4.20	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		3.80	Extensive

Experiential learning by the teachers as result of their explicit experiences is an opportunity for learners to apply what they've been taught to solve real-world challenges. Learners test their understanding of underlying principles, processes, and procedures and can experiment and adapt their practice to achieve the best outcomes (Kyeremeh et al., 2022). Experiential learning activities can include but are not limited to, hands-on laboratory experiments, internships, practicums, field exercises, study abroad, undergraduate research, and studio performances. In the perspective of Speicher (2021), who claimed that there is urgency for teacher educators to teach for social justice. Teacher's report feeling inadequately prepared to educate for social justice when entering the

classroom setting. Feelings of incompetence in social justice teaching expressed among preservice teachers coupled with minimal examination in the literature of the effects of teacher education practices that aid in the readiness to teach for social justice provided the foundation for this study. Teachers were able to conceptualize building communities with experiential methods to teach for social justice and how doing so created an effective learning community. Although teachers valued the implementation of experiential methods to foster the teaching of social justice, difficulties were expressed in their incorporation of experiential methods in the practicum environment due to a lack of confidence, teaching competence, or collegial support. On the other hand, Uzun

and Uygun (2022) aimed to reveal the effect of simulation-based experiential learning applications on gaining problem-solving skills in the Social Studies curriculum. According to research results, the post-test results of the experimental group students who were educated in the simulation-based experiential learning model were significantly higher than the control group students who were educated with the methods prescribed in the program. In conclusion, it has been reached that simulation-based experiential learning applications enhance students' problem-solving skills. Olovsson (2021) analyzed how teaching and learning take place in integrated social studies teaching in relation to various curriculum goals and what consequences the teaching has for students' approaches to learning. The grading in Year 6 contributes to the integrated teaching being more adapted and directed towards subject knowledge goals. Students are very committed and involved in higher degrees of integration and discourses of learning connected to overarching curriculum objectives and are more focused and performance-oriented when the subject knowledge discourse creates a dominant pattern. Teaching in social studies should consist of the whole range of learning

Technical skills are sets of abilities or knowledge used to perform practical tasks in the areas of science, the arts, technology, engineering, and math. Technical skills typically require the use of certain tools and the technologies required to use those tools. Technical skills are the abilities and knowledge needed to perform specific tasks. They are practical and often relate to mechanical, information technology, mathematical, or scientific tasks. Some examples include knowledge of programming languages, design programs, mechanical equipment, or tools (Coleman et al., 2020). Teachers must understand the material they teach. Naturally, different positions require various types

discourses, and how different knowledge conceptions can affect teaching and students' learning should also be considered.

3.1.3. Technical Skills—Further, Table 3 presents the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in terms of technical skills among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: offers alternative solutions and approaches; comes up with useful ideas (4.25) is always manifested, identifies relationships; expresses deep understanding (3.20) and anticipates consequences, plans ahead, acts on opportunities (3.13) are oftentimes manifested, while, concludes what's known and unknown; draws reasonable conclusions gives evidence to support them (2.31) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of the extent of critical thinking ability in terms of technical skills is 3.02, suggesting teachers' critical thinking abilities is moderately extensive. This indicates that the schools in Cateel 2 District are sometimes manifesting technical skills in their critical thinking abilities to improve teaching in Araling Panlipuan.

and levels of skill, but even teachers of very young children need significant expertise. It is not enough for a first-grade math teacher to know how to perform basic arithmetic, for example. Further, since knowledge is power, and the more your employees know, the more your business can grow. By providing technical skills training for your employees, you're instilling self-confidence that they have the knowledge and competence to perform their daily tasks to the best of their ability (Kyeremeh et al., 2022). On the other hand, Warner (2020) shared that technical skills are important in all industries. Most academic programs at higher education institutions focus on teaching technical skills.

Table 3. The Extent of Critical Thinking Ability Among Elementary Schools in Terms of Technical Skills

No	Technical Skills	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Identifies relationships; expresses deep understanding.	3.20	Extensive
2	Anticipates consequences, plans ahead, and acts on opportunities.	3.13	Extensive
3	Admits when things aren't feasible; looks for user-friendly solutions.	2.21	Less Extensive
4	Offers alternative solutions and approaches; comes up with useful ideas.	4.25	Very Extensive
5	Concludes what's known and unknown; draws reasonable conclusions and gives evidence to support them.	2.31	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.02	Moderately Extensive

However, in addition to seeking candidates with strong technical skills, employers also seek candidates who have strong soft skills, such as communication, organization, and teamwork. This paper highlights the importance of soft skills and how one academic program at a four-year institution incorporates teaching soft skills into courses in the curriculum to help best prepare its graduates for the professional world. Moreover, Çagir and Oruc (2020) explored the impacts of using intelligence and mind games on academic achievement, and students' attitudes towards Social Studies lessons were examined for the teaching of the concepts in the 6th grade Effective Citizenship Learning Area. As a result of the t-test analysis of the pre-post-application scores of attitudes in the control and experimental group, it was observed that there was a significant difference in favor of the post-test both in the control group and in the experimental group. As a result of the research, a conclusion was reached in favor of the experimental group in terms of both academic achievement and attitude towards the course. Intelligence and mind games can be used to teach the concepts of the Social Studies course.

3.1.4. Interpersonal Skills —Table 4 exhibits the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in terms of interpersonal skills among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: expresses appreciation of human differences related to values, culture, personality, or learning style preferences; adapts to preferences when feasible (4.31) and identifies learning needs; finds ways to overcome limitations, seeks out new knowledge (4.20) are always manifesting, and, identifies risks and problems with health care systems; promotes safety, quality, satisfaction, and cost containment (4.13) is oftentimes manifested, while, listens well; shows ability to imagine others' feelings and difficulties (3.25) is sometimes manifested, and promotes health; maximizes function, comfort, and convenience (2.21) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of the extent of critical thinking ability in terms of interpersonal skills is 3.62, suggesting teachers' critical thinking abilities is extensive. This indicates that the schools in Cateel 2 District are oftentimes manifesting interpersonal skills in their critical thinking abilities to

improve teaching in Araling Panlipuan. Good interpersonal skills involve insight, understanding, and the kind of social awareness that helps one determine what might be an 'appropriate' response in a given situation. There can be no set rules for determining this, much to the frustration of teachers and students alike' (Coleman, et.al 2020). A teacher must have strong interpersonal skills, particularly communication skills, which enables them to understand the require-

ments of each student. Moreover, the effectiveness of a teacher's interpersonal skills will enhance the quality of their lecture or teaching methods. Interpersonal skills are important for communicating and working with groups and individuals' personal and professional life. People with strong interpersonal skills tend to build good relationships and can work well with others. They understand family, friends, coworkers, and clients well.

Table 4. The Extent of Critical Thinking Ability Among Elementary Schools in Terms of Interpersonal Skills

No	Interpersonal Skills	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Identifies learning needs, finds ways to overcome limitations, and seeks out new knowledge.	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Identifies risks and problems with health care systems; promotes safety, quality, satisfaction, and cost containment.	4.13	Extensive
3	Promotes health; maximizes function, comfort, and convenience.	2.21	Less Extensive
4	Listens well; shows the ability to imagine others' feelings and difficulties.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
5	Expresses appreciation of human differences related to values, culture, personality, or learning style preferences; adapts to preferences when feasible.	4.31	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		3.62	Extensive

A social studies teacher demonstrates passion and commitment to your discipline. Outstanding candidates are able to multitask, source appropriate learning material, and also present their opinion to the class without making any student feel threatened for holding a different view. A teacher has to be aware and cares about people. The teacher collaborates and works with others well, comforting people when it is needed through good communication skills, and has the ability to perform conflict management

and resolution skills (Speicher, 2021). Meanwhile, Amolloh, Lilian, and Wanjiru (2018) believed that interpersonal skills require experiential learning for teacher educators to equip with opportunities for effective teaching and professional subjects, co-curricular activities, and micro-teaching vital for professional development. The experiential learning opportunities, conditional knowledge, preparedness, and performance during teaching practice provide the basis for predicting professional competence

and success for effective teaching. Conditional knowledge entails the application of critical thinking and problem-solving skills that demonstrate mastery of theoretical knowledge and professional practice across content, knowledge, skills, and insights. This type of knowledge and skills are developed through experiential learning coupled with effective preparedness for real-class instructional management. However, inadequate preparation in educational courses coupled with improper supervision and feedback impede effective professional development in most universities.

3.1.5. *Summary Of the Extent of Critical Thinking Ability*—Table 5 presents the summary

of the extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in Cateel 2 District in terms of its indicators, namely learning characteristics, experiential knowledge, technical skills, and interpersonal skills. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Learning Characteristics (4.20), experiential knowledge (3.80), interpersonal skills (3.62), and technical skills (3.02) exhibit that critical thinking abilities are oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive in their extent of critical thinking ability in improving teaching in Araling Panlipunan subject.

Table 5. Summary on the Extent of Critical Thinking Ability Among Elementary Schools in Cateel 2 District

No.	Critical Thinking Ability	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent (DI)
1	Learning Characteristics	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Experiential Knowledge	3.80	Extensive
3	Technical Skills	3.02	Moderately Extensive
4	Interpersonal Skills	3.62	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.66	Extensive

Developing critical thinking abilities translates to both academic and job success. Using these skills, students tend to expand the perspectives from which they view the world and increase their ability to navigate the important decisions in learning and in life. Asking questions enhances critical thinking in learning. One question may lead to another, and that will further help in clearing your concepts (Xhomara, 2022). It is very critical for teachers to gain awareness about the acquisition of critical thinking skills in the educational process. Given the scarcity of existing literature on teaching critical thinking skills and teachers’ perceptions and

views on the place of these skills in curricula, however, the present study is of great importance. Teachers demonstrated a high level of perception towards critical thinking skills. Furthermore, it was found that years of teaching experience and branch variables were significant predictors of critical thinking skills, whereas gender was not a significant predictor. Teachers reported that critical thinking skills are teachable while emphasizing that they are best taught in coordination with the course content. The challenges faced by teachers when teaching critical thinking skills include inadequate curriculum, overcrowded classrooms, inadequate teach-

ers, and anxiety about falling behind curriculum pacing (Kanmaz, 2022).

3.2. Extent Of Outcome-Focused Teaching—Adopting an outcome-focused approach means orienting the education to achieve outcomes where these are the results of activities. A focus on outcomes helps the teaching process prove to learners that what they are doing is working. In the field of education, an outcome focused is an outcome-based curriculum. Outcome-based education (OBE) is education in which an emphasis is placed on a clearly articulated idea of what students are expected to know and be able to do, that is, what skills and knowledge they need to have when they leave the school system (Polat, et al., 2022).

3.2.1. Intended Learning Outcome—Indicated in Table 6 is the extent of outcome-based teaching in terms of intended learning outcomes among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: The perception of value issues, from simple awareness through to the internalization of

The results revealed are supported by the study of Maksum, Widiana, and Marini (2021) aimed to analyze the effect of Self-Regulation, Social Skills, Critical Thinking, and Problem-Solving Skills on Social Learning Outcomes. The results showed there was a positive direct effect of self-regulation, social skills, critical thinking skills, and problem-solving skills on social studies learning outcomes on learning outcomes. This research implied that efforts to improve social studies learning outcomes began with improving self-regulation strategies, practicing social skills, developing critical thinking skills, and problem-solving skills. In addition, Labouta et al. (2019) investigated the intended, enacted, and perceived curriculum in an authentic research-based science program using curriculum mapping as a tool for analysis. Re-

personal value system (4.21), is always manifested, while refers to progressively complex manual o physical skills and the ability to use a complex piece of software, instrument or paper documentation (4.11) and intended to represent the nature of the competencies regarding the personal-epistemological and metacognitive development of students (4.08) are oftentimes manifested, and facilitate the knowledge in cognition, the progressively complex use of knowledge and artifacts (3.25) and refers to progressively complex levels in interpersonal communication, conflict resolution, collaboration and cross-cultural communication (3.25) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of outcome-focused teaching in terms of intended learning outcome is 3.78 or extensive. This means that the outcome-focused teaching is oftentimes manifested by the schools in Cateel 2 District. This indicates that the teachers in the respective schools are exhibiting an extensive intended learning outcome in teaching Araling Panlipunan subject.

sults of the curriculum mapping showed consistency and cogency of program and course-level learning outcomes. Students' perceptions of their authentic research experiences were well-aligned with the intended and enacted learning outcomes.

3.2.2. Infused Activities—Shown in Table 7 is the extent of outcome-based teaching in terms of infused activities among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Being open, aware, and compassionate toward diverse ideas, learning styles, entry points, experiences, and the uniqueness of an individual's story (4.21), which means that outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan is always manifested. Meanwhile, teachers are open beyond the four walls

Table 6. Extent of Outcome-Focused Teaching in Terms of Intended Learning Outcome

No	Intended Learning Outcome	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Intended to represent the nature of the competencies regarding the personal-epistemological and metacognitive development of students	4.08	Extensive
2	Facilitate the knowledge in cognition, the progressively complex use of knowledge and artifacts	3.25	Moderately Extensive
3	The perception of value issues, from simple awareness through to the internalization of personal value system	4.21	Very Extensive
4	Refers to progressively complex levels in interpersonal communication, conflict resolution, collaboration, and cross-cultural communication	3.25	Moderately Extensive
5	Refers to progressively complex manual or physical skills and the ability to use a complex piece of software, instrument, or paper documentation	4.11	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.78	Extensive

of the classroom. It lets people in and allows students outside of the room. Students are engaged in authentic learning, inquiry and real-life situations (4.18); respect for learning differences and racial and gender sensitivity (4.12); Being open, aware and compassionate toward diverse ideas, learning styles, entry points, experiences and the uniqueness of an individual's story (4.05); and It has student voice where start by simply changing the focus of questions and allowing them to have a say in their own learning will be

one of the best changes a teacher will ever make (3.85) suggest, outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan is oftentimes manifested. The overall mean rating of outcome-focused teaching in terms of infused activities is 4.08, suggesting that outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan is oftentimes manifested or extensive in nature in Cateel 2 District. This indicates that the teachers in the respective schools are exhibiting extensive infusing activities in teaching Araling Panlipunan subject.

The social studies course is one of the most appropriate courses for individuals to acquire social and cultural experiences and to have knowledge and experience in these subjects. The social studies course contains a lot of knowledge, skills, and values to enable the individual to know himself and gain a social identity. It is seen how a society expresses its feelings and emotions at different times, on sad or happy

days, through folk songs, which have an essential place among the literary products used in the course. In line with the data obtained, prospective teachers stated that they found the use of folk song-supported teaching activities in social studies teaching useful in ensuring permanence, drawing students' attention, and being fun. They also expressed that it has benefits such as giving an idea about our national

Table 7. Extent of Outcome-Based Teaching in Terms of Infused Activities

No	Infused Activities	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Respect for learning differences and racial and gender sensitivity.	4.12	Extensive
2	Being open, aware, and compassionate toward diverse ideas, learning styles, entry points, experiences, and the uniqueness of an individual’s story.	4.05	Extensive
3	It has student voice where starting by simply changing the focus of questions and allowing them to have a say in their own learning will be one of the best changes a teacher will ever make.	3.85	Extensive
4	Being open, aware, and compassionate toward diverse ideas, learning styles, entry points, experiences, and the uniqueness of an individual’s story.	4.21	Very Extensive
5	It is open beyond the four walls of the classroom. It lets people in and allows students outside of the room. Students are engaged in authentic learning, inquiry, and real-life situations.	4.18	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.08	Extensive

culture, presenting values to students, increasing intelligibility, ensuring that traditions and customs are conveyed from generation to generation, and providing students with different perspectives (Goksu, 2020). Uztemur, DInc, and Akun (2019) aimed to determine the usefulness of the teaching activities prepared for the effective utilization of museums and historical places in the context of grade seven social studies teaching to increase the efficiency of teaching-learning processes. The results of the research indicated that the implementation of the developed activities had positive outcomes in many respects. As a result of the implementation processes, the students have gained historical knowledge, developed historical and local awareness about Manisa, and understood the importance of historical and cultural values by means of comparing the past and present. Additionally, they have gained consciousness to protect and preserve the historical and cultural sites/artifacts. In terms of their social and emotional development, the participating students have developed friendship relations, group work competencies and empathy skills.

3.2.3. *Assessment*—Further, Table 8 presents the extent of outcome-based teach-

ing in terms of assessment among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Provide useful information about whether students have reached important learning goals and about the progress of each student (4.25); ensure that all students receive fair treatment in order not to limit students’ present and future opportunities and allow for multiple methods to assess student progress and for multiple but equivalent ways for students to express knowledge and understanding (4.25); employ practices and methods that are consistent with learning goals, curriculum, instruction, and current knowledge of how students learn (4.21); provide rigorous technical standards for assessment are developed and used to ensure high-quality assessments and to monitor the actual educational consequences of assessment use (4.21) suggest that the outcome-focused teaching in terms of assessment is always manifested. Meanwhile, the provision of instruction is a clear description of what the teacher wants to measure (4.08) suggests oftentimes manifested. The overall mean rating of outcome-focused teaching in terms of assessment is 4.20, suggesting that outcome-focused

teaching in terms of assessment in Araling Panlipunan is always manifested or very extensive in nature among schools in Cateel 2 District. This indicates that the teachers in the respective schools are exhibiting very extensive assessment strategies in teaching Araling Panlipunan subject. Hailikari et al. (2020) discussed that constructive alignment is often promoted as a principle to enhance the quality of learning, but the student perspective has often been neglected when exploring its influence on student learning.

Table 8. Extent of Outcome-Based Teaching in Terms of Assessment

No	Assessment	Mean (X)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Provides a clear description of what you want to measure.	4.08	Extensive
2	Provides useful information about whether students have reached important learning goals and about the progress of each student.	4.25	Very Extensive
3	Employs practices and methods that are consistent with learning goals, curriculum, instruction, and current knowledge of how students learn.	4.21	Very Extensive
4	Ensures that all students receive fair treatment in order not to limit students' present and future opportunities, and allows for multiple methods to assess student progress and for multiple but equivalent ways for students to express knowledge and understanding.	4.25	Very Extensive
5	Provides rigorous technical standards for assessment to ensure high-quality assessments and monitor the actual educational consequences of assessment use.	4.21	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.20	Very Extensive

The results show that different elements of constructive alignment had a clear role in guiding student learning. The teaching and assessment-related factors appeared to play a crucial role in guiding student learning and studying. Teaching and assessment that required students' active involvement clearly encouraged students to adopt a deep approach to learning, whereas the opposite was true for more traditionally organized courses. The intended learning outcomes did not seem to influence student learning much. The results also imply that the key is to find an optimal level of challenge

to support student learning and studying. The study deepens our understanding of the importance and influence of constructively aligned teaching to students' learning processes. Critical thinking is a key construct in social work education; however, a universally accepted definition of the construct remains elusive. To determine collective agreement in meaning and viable methods of assessment for critical thinking in social work education, Hall, Miller, and Tice (2021) administered an online survey to a national sample of social work educators. Findings supported social work educators' interest

in student reflection, intellectual curiosity, and analytical abilities.

3.3. *Outcome-Focused Teaching*—Table 9 presents the summary of the extent of outcome-focused teaching among teachers in terms of intended learning outcomes, infused activities, and assessment among schools in Cateel 2 District. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: assessment (4.20) is always manifested, while infused activities (4.08) and intended learning

outcomes are oftentimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.02 suggests that the extent of outcome-focused teaching among teachers is oftentimes manifested. This means that the outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan among Schools in Cateel 2 District is extensive. This suggests further that teachers think critically. They practice the thinking art of analyzing and evaluating as they consider both day-to-day activities and long-term teaching and learning goals.

Table 9. Summary on the Extent of Implementation of Schools’ Project Improvement

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent (DI)
1	Intended Learning Outcome	3.78	Extensive
2	Infused Activities	4.08	Extensive
3	Assessment	4.20	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.02	Extensive

Teachers evaluate what they have, determine what they will need, and decide how and when to assess student progress. In its most basic expression, critical thinking occurs when students are analyzing, evaluating, interpreting, or synthesizing information and applying creative thought to form an argument, solve a problem, or reach a conclusion (Alharbi, 2022).

3.4. *Relationship Between Critical Thinking Ability And Outcome-Focused Teaching Among Teachers*—It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between extent of critical thinking ability

($r=0.877$; $p<.001$) and outcome-focused teaching among schools in Cateel 2 District. Table 10 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between extent of critical thinking ability and outcome-focused teaching among schools in Cateel 2 District. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between critical thinking ability and outcome-focused teaching among teachers must be rejected for the results provided empirical evidence of significant results.

One of the core critical thinking skills a person needs every day is the ability to examine the implications and consequences of a belief or action. In its deepest form, this ability can help form a set of beliefs in everything from climate change to religion. In order to live a

meaningful life and to structure lives accordingly, there is a need to justify and reflect on values and decisions (Situmorang, 2022). Critical thinking helps students to filter the wheat from the chaff, intellectually speaking. Developing strong critical thinking skills helps stu-

Table 10. Significant Relationship Between Critical Thinking Ability and Outcome-Focused Teaching

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Critical Thinking Ability	0.877	<0.001	Significant	Reject H ₀

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

dents to eliminate dubious data to leave only the strongest, most reliable information. At its core, critical thinking is about having good reasons for our beliefs. It helps to navigate through bias (our own and that of others) to avoid manipulation or becoming enslaved by our feelings. These are essential skills in an age of overwhelming information. Helping students to develop critical thinking skills not only inoculates them against embracing flawed ideas, but these skills are also some of the most in-demand by employers, and this looks set to continue to be so well into the future. There are any number of ways to introduce critical thinking into the classroom, either as discrete activities or interwoven into lessons with other stated objectives. However, it is helpful to students to take the time to teach a variety of strategies to help them think critically about the ideas they encounter, which will help them form their own opinions (Alharbi, 2022). An opinion based on critical thinking does not rely on gut feeling but rather on rational reasoning, which often requires some form of initial research. On the other hand, Evangelisto (2021) argued that there is evidence in the literature that teaching critical thinking helps students gain critical thinking skills. However, students are not learning the critical thinking skills that teachers are doing to teach critical thinking skills. The findings of the study included descriptions of modeling critical thinking skills, allowing students to practice

using the skills and assessing the critical thinking skills using a skills-based assessment. The described useful techniques also included the requirement of analysis throughout, including analysis of data, analysis of the process, and analysis of thinking.

3.5. *Indicators of critical thinking ability that significantly influence level of outcome-focused teaching among teachers*—Table 11 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence on indicators of critical thinking ability that significantly influence level of outcome-focused teaching among teachers in Cateel 2 District. All indicators of critical thinking ability, such as experiential knowledge (0.002), technical skills (0.152), and interpersonal skills (0.001), except learning characteristics (0.344), indicate statistically significant to influence outcome-focused teaching in Cateel 2 District Schools. This shows that the extent of critical thinking ability of teachers provided direct influences on their extent of outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.895 suggests that the critical thinking ability accounts for 89.5 percent of the variance of outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan. This provides empirical evidence that the variability of outcome-focused teaching of teachers can be accounted for and be explained by the indicators as enumerated under the extent of critical thinking abilities of teachers in Cateel 2 District Schools.

Table 11. Regression coefficient analysis on the critical thinking ability that significantly influences outcome-focused teaching

Model	Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	<P
H ₀ (Intercept)	3.356	0.056		60.083	<0.287
H ₁ (Intercept)	0.167	0.157		1.069	<0.344
Learning Characteristics	0.086	0.091	0.100	0.949	<0.002
Experiential Knowledge	0.132	0.092	0.158	1.444	<0.015
Technical Skills	0.203	0.082	0.257	2.472	<.001
Interpersonal Skills	0.337	0.073	0.425	4.638	<.001

R² = 0.895

F-value = 116.350

p-value = < .001

In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (116.350) and F-statistic are significant $p < .001$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of outcome-focused teaching among schools. Coleman et al. (2020) explored that interpersonal skills can be developed through experiential learning, which is fundamental to social science education. Current literature indicates some methods of pedagogically implementing experiential learning are more effective than others. The Authors examined the effects of reflection type and abstraction order on content knowledge and content knowledge retention when teaching experientially. The findings of this study indicated neither the method in which students reflected, nor the order in which they received abstraction affected students' ability to attain content knowledge. However, when analyzing student content knowledge retention, a statistically significant interaction effect indicated reflection type and abstraction order were dependent upon one another. It is recommended those who are interested in knowledge retention outcomes should implement purposeful reflection-on-action tech-

niques when delivering abstract conceptualization prior to an experience. In the same manner, Ineç (2021) said that the stages of creating a dynamic map in Microsoft Excel with the rapid prototyping instructional design model developed by Tripp and Bichelmeyer are explained to support and improve students' global awareness in social studies lessons in Turkey. The dynamic map can reflect the acquisitions, concretize the content, and increase students' map literacy levels, but it also requires teacher support. In addition, the map also supports the competencies in teaching programs with mathematics and learning skills. Similarly, Capin et al. (2021) claimed that teaching vocabulary and reading comprehension during social studies instruction is critical for reading development and the acquisition of content knowledge. They systematically investigated how elementary teachers integrate vocabulary and reading comprehension instruction during social studies teaching, as well as the extent to which this instruction aligned with evidence-based practices. Findings revealed that two-thirds of social studies instructional time integrated practices for developing vocabulary and reading comprehension. Yet, the approaches for teaching compre-

hension and methods for instructional delivery (e.g., explicit instruction, high-quality feedback) teachers used infrequently aligned with those identified as effective in previous research. Further, Sömen (2021) discussed that in the teaching process of Social Studies courses, which includes many disciplines, including literature, students have a chance to increase their interest in different subjects and to develop their mental skills as well. The author aimed to determine the opinions of prospective teachers and middle school students about the use of literary materials as teaching/learning materials in the Social Studies course. The results showed that both the prospective teachers of Social Studies and the 6th-grade students who participated in the study were of the opinion that the use of literary

materials helped a lot to increase class participation and provided an enjoyable teaching/learning atmosphere. Therefore, the hypothesis stating among the indicators of critical thinking ability that significantly influence the level of outcome-focused teaching among teachers must be rejected. The results are further corroborated by the posed theory that implementation of outcome-based education is focused on the idea that people should be at the center of their own care and support planning and learning and that these learners should be actively listened to without judgment for their personal strengths should be acknowledged and reiterated through supporting what they have identified and what they want to achieve.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings were based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions were based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in Cateel 2 District in terms of learning characteristics (4.20), experiential knowledge (3.80), interpersonal skills (3.62), and technical skills (3.02) were oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive in improving teaching in Araling Panlipunan subject. The extent of outcome-focused teaching among teachers in terms of assessment (4.20) was always manifested, while infused activities (4.08) and intended learning outcomes are oftentimes manifested; thus, extensive outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan among Schools in Cateel 2 District. Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between critical thinking ability ($r=0.877$; $p<.001$) and outcome-focused teaching among

schools in Cateel 2 District. Indicators of critical thinking ability provided, namely, experiential knowledge (0.002), technical skills (0.015), and interpersonal skills (0.001), indicate a statistically significant influence on outcome-focused teaching among schools in Cateel 2 District.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions to wit; The extent of critical thinking ability among elementary teachers in Cateel 2 District regarding learning characteristics, experiential knowledge, interpersonal skills, and technical skills are often manifested, thus, extensively improving teaching in Araling Panlipunan subject. The extent of outcome-focused teaching among teachers in terms of assessment is always manifested. In contrast, infused activities and intended learning outcomes were oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive

in the outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan among Schools in Cateel 2 District. There was a significant relationship between critical thinking abilities and outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan among schools in Cateel 2 District. Indicators of critical thinking abilities provided, namely experiential knowledge, technical skills, and interpersonal skills, indicate a statistically significant influence of outcome-focused teaching in Araling Panlipunan among schools in Cateel 2 District.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations, to wit; The Public School District Supervisor in Cateel 2 District may consider other factors that contribute to the improvement of outcome-focused teaching not only in Araling Panlipunan but also across learning areas through conducting a School Learning

Action Cell, monitoring and adjusting curriculum management, and assessing learning outcomes as policy inputs. School Heads in Cateel 2 District may sustain practices intensifying critical thinking abilities in pedagogy and assessment through collaboration among teachers and their respective schools, which would enabled them to do the same and continuously improve themselves. Other factors that may influence schools' project effectiveness in curriculum and instruction may be explored, and the results utilized may be considered. Future research may include the underlying empirical investigations on the process and mechanism of teaching practices using innovative projects in schools and other initiatives to improve professional growth and to enhance and be included in the planning process cycle, implementation steps, and evaluation mechanisms.

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